

Effortless Access to Household Pulse Survey Datasets with 'hpsr': An R Data Package

Prasad Bhoite, MS, MPH, MBA¹, Christopher Clark, MSIS¹, Krupa Patel¹,
Rachel Clarke, PhD, CHES¹, Nana Garba, MD, PhD²

¹Department of Humanities, Health, and Society, Herbert Wertheim College of Medicine,
Florida International University, Miami, FL

²Department of Medical Education, Herbert Wertheim College of Medicine, Florida
International University, Miami, FL

Abstract

This project introduces an R package that significantly enhances the extraction, storage, and access to Household Pulse Survey data, which is crucial for research on the impact of COVID-19 in the United States (U.S.). By converting raw Census CSV files into Parquet and later into .rda formats, the package optimizes data management and efficiency. Researchers can easily access multiple survey datasets without needing to install them locally, saving memory and computational resources. Users can create tailored data subsets for specific research topics, making this package especially beneficial for studying COVID-19's effects across various demographics in the U.S. Additionally, the package is an excellent resource for students, offering a practical tool for class projects. The package, containing 63 datasets, is shared on GitHub as an open-source resource, fostering wider collaboration and use in the data science community.

Key Words: Household Pulse Survey, COVID-19 Impact, R Package Development

1. Introduction

This R Package provides easy access to the Household Pulse Survey data, offering a multifaceted view of the impact of COVID-19 on the U.S. population (US Census Bureau). The project focuses on the development of an R package, employing tools such as usethis, Rtools, and R Studio. The methodology involves downloading CSV files from the Census website, optimizing storage efficiency through Parquet conversion and easy storage on Github, further transforming these files into .rda datasets. The culminating step involves sharing the comprehensive package on GitHub as an open-source contribution to the field of data science.

2. Methodology

Leveraging usethis for project management and Rtools for efficient package building, our methodology initiates with the acquisition of raw data in CSV format from the US Census website (Pileggi, 2020; *R Packages (2e)*). A pivotal aspect of the process involves converting the CSV files to Parquet format, a step aimed at reducing file size without compromising data fidelity. Subsequently, the Parquet files are further transformed into .rda datasets, aligning with R's native data format. The entire workflow is orchestrated within R Studio, ensuring a streamlined and reproducible process (*Building R Packages with Devtools and Usethis | RStudio*). Figures 1 and 2 show the workflows associated with the creation of this data package.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 1: Infographic of the general steps taken to prepare, create, and host the R Data Package.

Figure 2: Infographic of the detailed steps taken to create the R Data Package.

3. Results

The result of this meticulous approach is the development of an R package that encapsulates the diverse insights from the Household Pulse Survey data. The optimized data processing pipeline, involving CSV to Parquet to .rda conversion, enhances the accessibility and efficiency of data retrieval for researchers and analysts. The finalized package, including 63 transformed datasets, is then shared on GitHub as an open-source contribution, fostering collaboration, transparency, and wider utilization in the data science community.

4. Discussion

We delve into the broader implications of this workflow, emphasizing the role of open-source contribution in advancing data science practices. The efficiency gains from the conversion of CSV to Parquet contribute not only to storage optimization but also faster data retrieval. The adoption of .rda datasets ensures compatibility and flexibility for diverse analyses. The GitHub repository serves as a dynamic hub for community engagement, enabling continuous improvement, collaboration, and broader utilization of the developed R package. The open-source nature encourages feedback, contributions, and applications in varied data science contexts, reinforcing its impact and relevance in the field (*PsyTeachR*).

4.1 Potential Applications

This R package facilitates the easy retrieval of the multiple rounds of Household Pulse Survey datasets to analyze the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the United States population. Downloading and storing the 63 rounds of large datasets individually is a cumbersome process. This package provides an easy access and retrieval of the multiple datasets and its codebook.

4.2 Limitations

This data package has 63 datasets with large size even after using different data compression techniques such as parquet file format, "LazyDataCompression" (R Core Team). Most likely, this package will not get accepted on The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) as they accept data packages with data size less than 5 MB. Also, when you install the package for the first time, it takes relatively long time.

4.3 Package Installation

You can download the latest development version from Github using the following command:

```
# install.packages("devtools")
devtools::install_github('prasadbhoite/hpsr')
```

If the above method of installation fails, you can use the following code that additionally specifies git branch and timeout argument:

```
# install.packages("devtools")
options(timeout=400)
devtools::install_github('prasadbhoite/hpsr', ref = 'master')
```

4.4 Usage: Datasets

To get the specific week of data, you need to use ‘data’ function and mention numerical dataset number of the Household Pulse Survey. Get started with hpsr with the following command:

```
hpsr::data('data_week1')
hpsr::data('data_week2')
hpsr::data('data_week3')
# ...
# ...
# ...
hpsr::data('data_week63')
```

4.5 Usage: Codebooks

To get the codebook for the individual datasets, go to the following link on the package website: <https://prasadbhoite.github.io/hpsr/reference/index.html>

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to Florida International University for their continuous support and resources that made this work possible. We also extend my appreciation to the U.S. Census Bureau for providing the publicly accessible Household Pulse Survey datasets, which were instrumental in the development of this project. Additionally, we would like to acknowledge the public use data science community for their invaluable contributions and shared knowledge, which have greatly enhanced the accessibility and usability of public datasets.

References

1. US Census Bureau. *Household Pulse Survey: Measuring Emergent Social and Economic Matters Facing U.S. Households*. Census.Gov. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.census.gov/householdpulsedata>
2. R Core Team. *Writing R Extensions*. CRAN. <https://cran.r-project.org/doc/manuals/R-exts.html>
R Packages (2e). (n.d.). Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://r-pkgs.org/>
3. Pileggi, S. (2020). *PIPING HOT DATA: Your first R package in 1 hour*. <https://www.pipinghotdata.com/posts/2020-10-25-your-first-r-package-in-1-hour/>
4. *Building R packages with devtools and usethis / RStudio*. [Video recording]. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EpTkT6Rkgbs>
5. *PsyTeachR*. PsyTeachR. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://psyteachr.github.io/>